

THE TASK OF EVALUATING PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS RELATED TO THE CONCEPT OF “TASTE” IN THE LANGUAGES CONTRASTING

Mamajonova E'zoxon Madaminjon qizi

Doctoral candidate of Andijan State University, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7524431>

Annotation: In the article, the task of evaluating the phraseological units related to the concept of “taste” the languages being studied is highlighted on the basis of examples.

Key words: Taste, concept, phraseological unit, the task of evaluating, contrastive, sentences.

Different structural types of phraseological units in the languages contrasting are characterized by the task of naming an object or event, as well as giving them a negative or positive evaluation. Evaluation means giving a negative or positive description of things.

Any phraseological units are not evaluative. But when interpreting the meaning of the compound, its evaluation feature is definitely involved. If there is an evaluation scheme in the semantic structure of phraseological units, regardless of the structural-grammatical construction of that phrase, the explanation of the phrase is given by an adjective, or words such as — “ниҳоятда”, — “жуда” representing the evaluation scheme were used in this explanation. For example, аччиғи чиқди, аччиғи қистади, аччиғидан тушди – the first meaning is pepper added to food or a flavoring mixture, the second meaning мазаси қочди, мазасини қочирди, мазаси кетди – the first meaning is whose, the taste of what's gone, missed the taste or missed the pleasure. Such phraseological units are found in English. For example, leave a bitter taste in (one's) mouth - left a bad impression or all his wishes came to naught, leave a sour taste in (one's) mouth - the first meaning is translated as leaving a sour taste in the mouth, and the second meaning means having a negative impact.

In Uzbek: Ошга солинган қалампирни аччиғи чиқиб кетибди [Ойбек, Олтин водийдан шабадалар]; Бу гапни эшитиб, ойимнинг аччиғи чиқиб кетди [Ҳ.Назир, “Чўл ҳавоси”]; Ботиржон, сал мазам қочди. Бошим айланиб, кўзим тиняпти. Кета қолай (Саид Аҳмад, “Хукм”). Аммо кейинги вақтда савдонинг мазаси кетди [С.Анорбоев, “Оқсой”]; Охирида қўшилган холва таомни мазасини қочириб юборибди [Ш.Тошматов, “Эрк қуши”];

In English:

1) I know Kelly's your friend, but she was so rude at dinner—it just left a sour taste in my mouth [4,66].

2) Of course Andrew not inviting me to his party leaves a sour taste in my mouth [3,156];

1) I don't know, man, the fact that he lied to us just leaves a bitter taste in the mouth [2,146].

2) The way they conducted the interview left a bitter taste in the mouth. I don't think I'd accept the job even if they offered it [1,28].

A certain part of phraseological units with “taste-ta'm-maza” component names an event and gives them a negative or positive evaluation tone. For example:

In Uzbek: маза қочирувчи, нордони чиқди, аччиқ таъми бермоқ, шириндимоғ бўлмоқ, шўри чиқиб кетмоқ, шўрига шўрва тўкилмоқ, нимтатир қилмоқ; М;, Зумрад нимтатир қилиб чой дамлаб қўйди [Ойбек, “Зумрад”], аччиқ қилмоқ, аччиқ-чучук тайёрламоқ; М;, Чорпояда оёқ узатиб, ўнг чоғли киши чой ичар, бирови аччиқ-чучук тайёрлаб, бирови турп майдаларди [С.Нуров, Нарвон], кўзига чўп солмоқ, қош қўяман деб кўз чиқармоқ, кўргани кўзи йўқ, қўл кўтармоқ(урмоқ маъносида);

In English: so bad one can taste it, in bad taste, the worst possible, etc. taste, leave a bitter taste in (one's) mouth, leave a bad taste in the/your mouth, in poor taste, a bitter pill to swallow, be bitter and twisted, fight till the bitter end, fight to the bitter end, fight until the bitter end, end on a sour note, finish on a sour note, go sour, hit a sour note, leave a sour taste in (one's) mouth, sound a sour note, sour cherry, salt mines, salt of the earth, salty dog, salty tongue, phrases such as perform the function of negative evaluation, in the following phraseological units,

In Uzbek: маза бермоқ, маза киритмоқ, ширин бўлмоқ, чучук сув, ширинлагани келмоқ (Чойингларни ширинлагани келдим [И.Раҳим, “Чин муҳаббат”]);

In English: taste like (something), all (one's) taste is in (one's) mouth, be in good taste, the best possible, etc. taste, have good taste, have expensive taste(s), leave a nasty taste in (one's) mouth, talk and taste your tongue, leave a sour taste in (one's) mouth ,(as) sweet as honey, (as) sweet as pie, (as) sweet as sugar, a rose by any other name (would smell as sweet), a sweet tooth, be short and sweet, be sweet on (one), cop it sweet a positive evaluation is visible in phrases like.

One phraseological combination can express both positive and negative meaning at the same time. This phenomenon is called phraseological enantiosemia in linguistics. For example, in English, the first meaning of the phraseology of a question of taste is to enjoy food or drink, and the second meaning expresses human taste and views. For example, in this sentence it can come in two

different translations: "I can't believe you hate Cilantro, but I guess it's just a question of taste" – 1. Силантрони (Мексика ва Хиндистонда ўстириладиган аччиқ ўсимлик) ёмон кўришингизга ишонмайман, лекин менимча, бу шунчаки дидга боғлиқ. 2. Силантрони (тайёрланган овқатини) ёмон кўришингизга ишонмайман аммо билимшимча у инсонга завқ бағишлайди.

There are such phraseological units in the Uzbek language, the first meaning of the phrase *мазасини олмоқ* is to embarrass, embarrass, and put a person in an uncomfortable situation with words and actions, while the second meaning is in any speech or translated as “овосини олмоқ, мазасини тотимоқ, роҳатланмоқ” can come For example: Исмат отанинг бу гапи ҳам, чойхўрларнинг маъқулловчи кулгулари ҳам мулла Бердиёрнинг мазасини оларди [Муштум, 1994 й].

Phraseological units with an evaluation feature in the languages contrasting are considered active characterizing tools in artistic texts. With their help, different attitudes of the lyrical hero to various events and objects are expressed, the hero of one work describes another with the help of such phrases. In Uzbek: Қойил қолиш керак-да! Қатновчилар ... Маҳмуд аканинг мантисига мазахўрак бўлиб қолган эдилар [Н.Сафаров, “Узоқни кўзлаган қиз”]; In English: Some people thought that wearing such a bright outfit to a funeral was in really bad taste, but it was meant to be a tribute to his friend [BNC. В78.- 2139 p]. Баъзи одамлар дафн маросимида бундай ёрқин кийим кийиш бепаросатлик деб ўйлашди, лекин у яқин инсонига хурматни англатади.

References:

1. Daley J, Smithonian, “Restorations Botches 16th Century Spanish Statue of Saint, 2018; - 28 p
2. Tell me about, Chancellor press, 2011; - 146 p
3. Updike J., The Lucid eye in silver town - 156 p
4. Zindell, David THE BROKEN GOD, 2001; - 66 p

